

Biodiversity, Occurrence, and Habitat Associations of Freshwater Crabs in Mara Tangi Stream, District Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

*The diversity and distribution of freshwater crabs remain understudied in many semi-arid stream systems of Pakistan. Crabs are considered major contributors to the ecology of several inland aquatic systems. This study investigated the relative abundance, distribution and morphological characteristics of freshwater crabs and assessed the conditions of their habitat in the Mara Tangi Stream, District Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan. In the summer and based on the dominant microhabitat conditions of the stream, field surveys (visual encounter surveys, hand sampling and trapping) were conducted. Captured crabs were subject to morphological identification and measurement of carapace (length and width) and weight. These crabs were then returned to the site of capture. Data pertaining to the habitat conditions and water quality were documented to interpret the occurrence of the species. A total of two species and nine samples were documented, including *Potamon fluviatile* ($n = 6$; 66.67%) and *Potamon ibericum* ($n = 3$; 33.33%). While species richness was low ($S = 2$), diversity was of a moderate level (Shannon-Wiener index = 0.637; Simpson diversity index = 0.444) and evenness was high (Pielou's $J = 0.918$). *Potamon fluviatile* was observed to have a greater mean of carapace length and width as well as greater weight than *P. ibericum*. The dominant characteristics of the stream were slow to moderate flow with a slight alkalinity and super saturation of dissolved oxygen. *Potamon fluviatile* was associated with deeper and faster flowing microhabitats, while *P. ibericum* was associated with shallow microhabitats with slow flow. The results establish preliminary data for freshwater crab surveys throughout Balochistan. In addition, the results advocate for the protection of small, semi-arid stream habitats from disruption, water extraction, and degradation of the stream banks.*

1. Introduction

Freshwater ecosystems create habitats that are vital for sustaining many ecological processes and are home to a remarkable assemblage of both vertebrate and invertebrate fauna (Dudgeon et al. 2006; Reid et al. 2019; Tickner et al. 2020). Streams, rivers, and wetlands are important inland waters systems and help sustain a high level of biodiversity and a variety of ecological processes, such as the cycling of nutrients and the decomposition of organic matter. These systems also sustain many of the interactions that comprise various food webs in both aquatic and riparian environments. Unfortunately, freshwater systems are among the most impacted ecosystems of all because of the multiple and cumulative impacts of numerous stressors, such as pollution, flow alterations, water abstraction, habitat destruction, agrochemical runoff, and climate change among others (Sayer et al. 2025).

Freshwater crabs are true decapods of the Brachyura that live either in freshwater or in humid, moist terrestrial environments where they complete their life cycles. They are found in large and small geographic ranges through much of the tropics and subtropics and are of particular interest in regions such as Asia, Africa, and the Neotropics (Yeo et al. 2008). Many freshwater crab species have small geographic ranges because of their reliance on aquatic environments and their low ability to disperse and direct development (Cumberlidge et al. 2009; Cumberlidge and Ng 2009). These traits enable them to serve as excellent indicators of the state of freshwater habitats, including habitat continuity, but makes them susceptible to disturbances and loss of their habitats.

Freshwater crabs act as omnivores, detritivores, predators, scavengers, and prey in their respective ecosystems. They aid in the breakdown of leaf litter, process organic matter, disturb sediment, and help in nutrient distribution because of their feeding and burrowing activities in stream ecosystems (Harlioğlu et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2020). They require certain habitat structures which include stones, submerged roots and burrows, shaded banks, muddy margins, vegetation, and refuge areas where the water flow is slow (Farhadi & Harlioğlu, 2018). It is therefore evident that the presence of freshwater crabs is an indicator of stream health and biodiversity.

Research on freshwater crabs in Pakistan is still in its early stages, especially in the under studied semi-arid regions such as Balochistan. Existing literature has identified freshwater crabs in the streams of Nushki, Harnai, Loralai, and regions of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, however, many of the streams remain unexplored (Soomro & Dastagir, 2019; Nawaz et al., 2022; Soomro et al., 2022). This gap in research is critical because the small streams of semi-arid regions may be the only sustaining areas for freshwater species and may be very vulnerable to activities such as seasonal drought, livestock, agricultural, and other disturbances.

Mara Tangi stream in Loralai, Balochistan is a freshwater stream of a semi-arid zone where there has been no previous research to establish a presence/absence baseline of freshwater crabs and their habitat associations. This study aimed to identify the species of freshwater crabs, assess their abundance, identify size/shape differences (morphometrics), assess habitat and water quality, as well as justify the observed assemblage from an ecological and conservation standpoint.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study focused on the Mara Tangi Stream located in the District Loralai of the Balochistan region in Pakistan. This stream encompasses the semi-arid region of northern Balochistan, which is home to varying types of microhabitats. These include rocky, gravelly and muddy stream substrates, pools, aquatic macrophytes, and vegetated stream banks. The neighboring areas include habitat patches resulting from agricultural and pastoral land uses, as well as from local water consumption. Sample collection sites were selected based on stream sections that were accessible and that represented varying habitat conditions.

2.2 Field sampling and specimen handling

An ecological survey design based on field sampling was employed for this study. Freshwater crabs were sampled in summer using the following techniques: visual encounter survey, hand collection, dip nets, and baited traps. Searches were made along stream banks, and within and beneath stones, burrows, and vegetation, and in shallow water where it was assumed crabs would be present. It was ensured that the collected crabs were retained only temporarily to allow for identification, photography, and measurement, after which the crabs were released at the sites of collection to minimize disturbance to the local population.

2.3 Species identification and morphometric measurements

Freshwater crabs were identified based on their external morphological characters and using regional taxonomic literature. External morphological characters included shapes of the carapace and of the chela, as well as proportions of the body and the texture of the carapace. The abdominal morphology was also examined. Standard measurements of each of the sampled crabs in the form of carapace length and width and body weight were recorded. For each species, measurements were reported as mean and standard deviation.

2.4 Habitat and water-quality assessment

Habitat characteristics where crabs were found were assessed, including stream width, water depth, flow velocity, and percent cover of vegetation. Water quality parameters were measured as pH, dissolved oxygen, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, turbidity, and salinity. These variables were assessed to describe the Mara Tangi Stream and the associated ecological conditions in the habitat of each recorded crab species.

2.5 Diversity and statistical analysis

Relative abundance was estimated based on the number of individuals represented by each species. Species richness was described using the Margalef richness index, while the Shannon-Wiener diversity index and Simpson diversity index were used to describe species diversity. Pielou's index was used to describe species evenness (Magurran, 2004). Morphometric, habitat, and water quality data were subjected to descriptive statistics. The relationships among carapace length, carapace width, and body weight were assessed using Pearson correlation coefficients.

3. Results

3.1 Species occurrence and relative abundance

Two species of freshwater crabs were found from Mara Tangi Stream, namely: *Potamon fluviatile* and *P. ibericum*. Total of nine individuals were collected and identified. *P. fluviatile* was the more abundant species with six individuals (66.67% of the total collected), whilst *P. ibericum* had three individuals (33.33%). Dominance of *P. fluviatile* aside, occurrence of both species indicates that Mara Tangi Stream is likely a suitable habitat for freshwater crabs.

Figure 1. Location of Mara Tangi Stream and relative abundance of the recorded freshwater crab species in District Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan.

Table 1. Relative abundance of freshwater crab species recorded in Mara Tangi Stream.

Species	Number of individuals (n)	Relative abundance (%)
<i>Potamon fluviatile</i>	6	66.67
<i>Potamon ibericum</i>	3	33.33
Total	9	100.00

Table 2. Diversity indices for freshwater crabs recorded in Mara Tangi Stream.

Diversity attribute	Value
Total individuals (N)	9
Species richness (S)	2
Margalef richness index	0.455

Shannon-Wiener index (H')	0.637
Simpson diversity index (1 - D)	0.444
Pielou's evenness (J')	0.918

The survey recorded low species richness ($S = 2$) for the collection. However, diversity of the assemblage was found to be moderate according to the Shannon-Wiener (0.637) and Simpson diversity (0.444) indices. Pielou's evenness (0.918) indicated that even though one species was more abundant, the two recorded species were not extremely unevenly represented, and were relatively balanced.

3.2 Morphological description and morphometric variation

Potamon fluviatile had an Olive brown to dark brown, and slightly granulated carapace, which was transversely oval and moderately convex with a dull granulated dorsal surface. The Chelipeds were robust and the walking legs were of slender to moderately stout with a ventral surface of pale whitish to cream with a slight tinge of orange. In comparison, *P. ibericum* had a strongly convex, carapace with a strongly granulated dorsal surface, strongly convex and rasped carapace and a dorsal surface with a color range from dark brown to blackish brown and appendices of an orange to reddish orange coloration. These external morphological characteristics greatly aided in the field identification of the two species

Figure 2. Comparative morphology of *Potamon fluviatile* (A-C) and *Potamon ibericum* (D-F) recorded from Mara Tangi Stream.

Morphometric measurements between these two species exhibited significant differences. *P. fluviatile* was the largest species, having larger measurements for carapace length (45.10 ± 4.92 mm), carapace width (55.90 ± 6.41 mm), and weight (40.83 ± 13.64 g) as compared to *P. ibericum*. The

later species had smaller measurements for carapace length (31.23 ± 2.75 mm), carapace width (39.13 ± 3.35 mm), and weight (11.83 ± 3.51 g).

Table 3. Morphometric attributes of freshwater crab species recorded in Mara Tangi Stream.

Species	n	Carapace length (mm) \pm SD	Carapace width (mm) \pm SD	Body weight (g) \pm SD
Potamon fluviatile	6	45.10 ± 4.92	55.90 ± 6.41	40.83 ± 13.64
Potamon ibericum	3	31.23 ± 2.75	39.13 ± 3.35	11.83 ± 3.51

3.3 Habitat and water-quality conditions

Habitat descriptions of the freshwater crabs extended from shallow to moderately deep streams with moderate to high amounts of submerged or emergent vegetation to stretches where the stream was particularly slow flowing. The average stream width was 3.20 ± 0.00 m, with a mean water depth of 15.89 ± 8.22 cm, and a mean flow velocity of 0.15 ± 0.12 m/s. Vegetation density was approximately 36.78 ± 4.12 %. Water of ecosystems in this study was reported as slightly alkaline (pH 7.76 ± 0.11). It was described as well oxygenated with a mean of 8.36 ± 0.23 mg/L of dissolved oxygen. Conductivity was of a mean of 419.56 ± 17.78 μ S/cm, with total dissolved solids of 210.00 ± 9.00 mg/L with a mean turbidity of 3.17 ± 0.035 NTU and a mean salinity of 0.20 ± 0.02 ppt.

Table 4. Overall morphometric, habitat, and water-quality characteristics of sampled freshwater crabs and their habitats.

Variable	Mean \pm SD	Minimum	Maximum
Carapace length (mm)	40.48 ± 8.07	28.50	50.00
Carapace width (mm)	50.31 ± 9.94	35.80	62.50
Body weight (g)	31.17 ± 18.16	8.50	57.00
Stream width (m)	3.20 ± 0.00	3.20	3.20
Water depth (cm)	15.89 ± 8.22	5.00	30.00
Flow velocity (m s ⁻¹)	0.15 ± 0.12	0.02	0.38
Vegetation cover (%)	36.78 ± 4.12	30.00	43.00
pH	7.76 ± 0.11	7.60	7.90
Dissolved oxygen (mg L ⁻¹)	8.36 ± 0.23	8.00	8.70
Conductivity (μ S cm ⁻¹)	419.56 ± 17.78	390.00	445.00
Total dissolved solids (mg L ⁻¹)	210.00 ± 9.00	195.00	223.00

Turbidity (NTU)	3.17 ± 0.35	2.60	3.70
Salinity (ppt)	0.20 ± 0.02	0.17	0.23

Microhabitat partitioning was evident from the species-specific habitat summaries. *Potamon fluviatile* was found in environments characterized by deeper waters (19.67 ± 7.20 cm) and higher flow velocities (0.20 ± 0.12 m s⁻¹) when compared to environments occupied by *P. ibericum* which was found in shallower waters (8.33 ± 3.51 cm) and in slower flowing sections (0.06 ± 0.05 m s⁻¹). The presence of vegetation cover, pH, and dissolved oxygen did not differ between the two species. Therefore, the differences in water depth and flow may be the more important factors driving the local occurrence of the species at the sampled sites.

Table 5. Habitat and water-quality characteristics associated with each recorded freshwater crab species.

Habitat variable	Potamon fluviatile (n = 6)	Potamon ibericum (n = 3)
Water depth (cm)	19.67 ± 7.20	8.33 ± 3.51
Flow velocity (m s ⁻¹)	0.20 ± 0.12	0.06 ± 0.05
Vegetation cover (%)	37.67 ± 3.98	35.00 ± 4.58
Stream width (m)	3.20 ± 0.00	3.20 ± 0.00
pH	7.75 ± 0.10	7.77 ± 0.15
Dissolved oxygen (mg L ⁻¹)	8.35 ± 0.19	8.37 ± 0.35

3.4 Correlations among morphometric traits

Pearson correlation analysis demonstrated significant positive relations among carapace length, carapace width, and body weight. Carapace length and width had a correlation of $r = 0.998$, and $r = 0.997$ for body weight. Carapace width and body weight had a correlation of $r = 0.999$. From these results, it can be interpreted that there is proportional growth within the sampled individuals, and also, carapace dimensions can represent indicators of body size biomass. Since the sample size is small, it is important to consider these relations, and larger seasonal datasets should be collected for verification.

Figure 3. Pearson correlation heatmap showing relationships among morphometric parameters of freshwater crabs recorded in Mara Tangi Stream.

4. Discussion

This study reveals preliminary insights into Mara Tangi Stream, District Loralai, Balochistan, focusing on the habitat associations and biodiversity of freshwater crabs. The discovery of *Potamon fluviatile* and *P. ibericum* suggests the presence of freshwater crabs in the semiarid landscape of the region. The documentation of only nine individuals from two species is not ideal, but it is an important finding since the stream systems in Balochistan are largely undocumented, and locality-based surveys are essential for collection and illustration of regional freshwater biodiversity.

The presence of *P. fluviatile* suggests the possible greater tolerance of the species, or the possible greater adaptation of the species to the conditions present at Mara Tangi Stream, evidenced by the species' presence in deeper, faster flowing microhabitats. It is possible that the species may prefer aquatic microhabitats of more stable refuge, more highly oxygenated, or more highly augmented and less covered by vegetation. The presence of *P. ibericum* in the stream is indicative of a more rapid and less flowing microhabitat. The presence and absence of species is indicative of variable microhabitat, local abundance and possibly, species detectability during the survey. Regional studies have demonstrated the variability in the abundance and richness of freshwater crab species in Balochistan, determined by the seasonal variability of habitat, water quality, and substrate (Soomro & Dastagir, 2019; Nawaz et al., 2022; Soomro et al., 2022).

When interpreting the species richness of the Mara Tangi Stream, we must consider ecological factors. Freshwater crab assemblages can naturally have a low number of species due to

drainage isolation, limited dispersal, the size of the stream, and the stream's historical biogeography (Cumberlidge et al., 2009; Ghanavi et al., 2023). As a result, streams with low species richness can still be important environmentally, as they can provide a refuge habitat in a semi-arid region. The high evenness value suggests that both species had an important contribution to the assemblage in spite of the dominance of *P. fluviatile*. Sampling during the wet and dry seasons may provide an answer to whether species richness and abundance are variable or if they are constant over time.

The current samples provided evidence of clear morphometric differences of the two crab species. *Potamon fluviatile* were larger and heavier than *P. ibericum*. These differences could be attributed to differences in the microhabitat, bias during sampling, and the age structure of the crabs or the sex ratio. The relationships among the carapace lengths, carapace widths, and body weights suggest that the crabs were likely to be of proportional growth. Further studies to evaluate the structure of the populations and growth of the crabs should be conducted during the different seasons using larger samples.

Water quality data of Mara Tangi stream indicates that conditions were mostly suitable for freshwater crabs during the sampling period. pH levels slightly above neutrality along with high levels of dissolved oxygen, low salinity and low turbidity suggest that the sampled sections were not heavily impacted at the time of sampling. Some cover by flora may provide shelter, and food resources in the form of detritus, along with the stabilization of the banks. The shelter and food resources are important because freshwater crabs utilize stones, burrows, roots that are submerged, and vegetated margins in order to protect themselves from predators and strong currents, and to avoid drying out (Farhadi & Harlioğlu, 2018; Harlioğlu et al., 2017).

The function of the freshwater crabs that were sampled also should be taken into account. These crabs also help streams function by eating detritus, and by physically disturbing sediment and helping to break down the detritus, and by carrying out other important functions through their various interactions. Freshwater crabs are also important for linking the terrestrial and aquatic food webs (Yang et al., 2020; Wehrtmann et al., 2019). Although the present study did not measure ecosystem functions, the presence of freshwater crabs at this site indicates that they may be important for food webs and the cycling of organic matter.

The small, semi-arid ephemeral streams such as Mara Tangi have several threats from water extraction, runoff from agriculture, the introduction of domestic animals, and sedimentation along with pollution and removal of riparian vegetation. Freshwater crabs have a short range of dispersal. Thus, local habitat destruction will cause a reduction in population and possibly even local extinctions before the crustaceans have the opportunity to recolonize from the neighboring drainage systems. The most important actions to conserve the local crabs and the freshwater biodiversity will be maintaining water flow, protecting the riparian zone, minimizing pollution, and avoiding disturbance to stones, banks, and burrows.

The sample was small and the collections may not represent the full diversity of the stream in time and space. Freshwater crabs are often nocturnal and reside in burrows, so their destructibility

may depend on the time of day, temperature, water level, and season. As the identification of these species was based on morphology, it would be better to have a molecular confirmation of the species, as members of the *Potamon* genus may be differentiated depending on the isolation of the drainage systems as documented in previous findings (Afzali et al. 2024; Ghanavi et al. (2023).

5. Conclusion

We describe the occurrence of the freshwater crabs, *Potamon fluviatile* and *P. ibericum* in Mara Tangi Stream, District Loralai, Balochistan. *Potamon fluviatile* was the larger and more abundant of the two species. *P. ibericum* was the smaller and rarer species in the study area. The stream had slightly alkaline water, well oxygenated, with low to moderate current and vegetation. It was possible to hypothesize from the data available regarding the habitats of these species, that *P. fluviatile* was more prevalent in the deeper and stronger current areas of the stream, while *P. ibericum* was more common in the shallower and slower current areas. Although there were fewer species in the stream, the species that were available had moderate diversity and high evenness, suggesting that the Mara Tangi Stream is important as a local refuge for freshwater crabs. The study provides valuable and important information on freshwater crab habitats for future research and monitoring studies and also illustrates the necessity of conserving small freshwater habitats in the semi-arid region of Pakistan.

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